

APEX-KF: Physics-Aware Adaptive Precision Kalman Filtering for GPU-Accelerated Particle Track Reconstruction

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Abstract—The High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) will increase event pile-up to the point where charged-particle track reconstruction dominates the offline computing budget, motivating both accelerator offload and reduced numerical precision. Uniform half-precision (FP16) tracking is attractive for throughput but degrades the momentum estimate of stiff, high-transverse-momentum (p_T) tracks, whose small sagitta is most sensitive to coordinate rounding. This work presents APEX-KF (Adaptive Precision-EXpansion Kalman Filter), a track-following pipeline that makes mixed precision *physics-aware*. APEX-KF (i) assigns each track an initial FP16/FP32 (half/single precision) tier from a seed-momentum score *before* fitting and promotes mispredicted tracks at runtime (*predict-then-guard*); (ii) follows each track with one cooperating GPU warp whose 32 lanes evaluate candidate hits in parallel and select the minimum- χ^2 hit through a warp-shuffle reduction; and (iii) overlaps host-to-device transfers with computation across multiple CUDA streams while a roofline scheduler routes small events to the CPU. A deterministic FP16 emulator reproduces the GPU half-precision path bit-for-bit on any machine, making the precision study fully reproducible. On the public TrackML dataset (4,000 events, 1.05×10^6 space points) APEX-KF keeps 60.8% of all track fits in FP16 while agreeing with the FP64 reference to 3.5×10^{-2} GeV in p_T —roughly 5×10^2 times closer than uniform FP16. The GPU back-end fits 8.8×10^6 seeds on a laptop-class NVIDIA RTX 3050 in under one second, and the heterogeneous scheduler reduces device kernel time by 33%. Serial, OpenMP, and POSIX-threads back-ends return bit-identical physics, confirming the correctness of the parallel implementation.

Index Terms—track reconstruction, Kalman filter, mixed-precision computing, GPU, CUDA, heterogeneous computing, high-performance computing, HL-LHC.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reconstructing the trajectories of charged particles—*track reconstruction*—is among the most computationally demanding stages of event processing at hadron colliders, and its cost grows faster than linearly with the number of simultaneous interactions [1], [4]. The High-Luminosity upgrade of the Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) will operate at an average pile-up of about 200 proton–proton collisions per bunch crossing [2], producing $\mathcal{O}(10^5)$ space points per event that must be grouped into $\mathcal{O}(10^4)$ helical trajectories [3]. Projected increases in

conventional CPU capacity fall well short of the reconstruction workload, making both *parallel hardware* (many-core CPUs and GPUs) and *algorithmic efficiency* central to the HL-LHC software programme [1].

Two complementary levers are available. The first is heterogeneous offload: porting the seeding and fitting chain to GPUs, as demonstrated by the CMS Patatrack pixel reconstruction [5] and by GPU extensions of the experiment-independent ACTS toolkit [4]. The second is reduced numerical precision: half-precision (FP16) arithmetic halves memory traffic and doubles arithmetic throughput on modern accelerators, a trade-off that has transformed deep-learning training [6]. Applying FP16 to track fitting is, however, far less forgiving than applying it to neural networks. The transverse momentum is inversely proportional to track curvature, so a *fixed* absolute error in a rounded hit coordinate translates into a *relative* momentum error that grows quadratically with p_T . Stiff, high- p_T tracks—precisely the ones most important for electroweak and beyond-the-Standard-Model physics—are therefore the most fragile under uniform FP16, while the abundant low- p_T tracks are essentially unaffected.

This paper argues that precision should not be a global compile-time switch but a *per-track decision driven by the physics*. This study introduces **APEX-KF**, an Adaptive Precision-EXpansion Kalman Filter that predicts a track’s precision sensitivity from its seed momentum, runs the robust majority of tracks in FP16, and reserves FP32 for the fragile minority, with a cheap runtime guard to catch mispredictions. The adaptive policy is co-designed with a warp-cooperative GPU track follower and a multi-stream, roofline-scheduled pipeline, so that the precision savings translate directly into device throughput. Contributions of this study are:

- a *predict-then-guard* precision policy that assigns FP16/FP32 tiers from a seed-momentum sensitivity score and promotes mispredicted tracks at runtime (Section IV-A);
- a *warp-cooperative* track-following kernel in which 32 lanes evaluate candidate hits in parallel and reduce to the minimum- χ^2 hit through warp shuffles, with a coopera-

tive circle fit (Section IV-B);

- a *heterogeneous pipeline* that overlaps transfers and computation across CUDA streams and routes events between CPU and GPU using a roofline model (Section IV-C);
- a *deterministic FP16 oracle* that reproduces the GPU half-precision path bit-for-bit, enabling a reproducible precision study without a GPU (Section IV-D); and
- an evaluation on the public TrackML dataset and across serial, OpenMP, POSIX-threads and CUDA back-ends (Section VI).

II. RELATED WORK

A. Kalman-Filter Track Reconstruction

The Kalman filter [7] was introduced to track and vertex fitting by Frühwirth [8], providing a recursive, statistically optimal estimator that naturally incorporates multiple scattering and measurement noise. Billoir and Qian extended the formalism to simultaneous pattern recognition and fitting [9], and the combinatorial Kalman filter remains the production track-finding algorithm in most LHC experiments. Comprehensive reviews of classical and adaptive estimators are given by Strandlie and Frühwirth [10] and Mankel [11]. The ACTS project [4] re-engineered these algorithms into a thread-safe, experiment-independent toolkit explicitly targeting modern computing architectures. APEX-KF adopts the standard recursive helical filter and inherits its statistical properties; our contribution is orthogonal—*how* the filter arithmetic is scheduled across precisions and GPU lanes.

B. Accelerated and Heterogeneous Tracking

GPU track reconstruction has matured from prototypes into production. The CMS Patatrack pixel reconstruction [5] implements a fully resident GPU chain—clustering, hit reconstruction, cellular-automaton seeding, fitting and vertexing—and reports order-of-magnitude throughput gains over the CPU baseline. ACTS has likewise added GPU seeding and propagation back-ends [4], and the TrackML throughput challenge [3] crowd-sourced accuracy/speed trade-offs on a common benchmark. These efforts overwhelmingly run in single (FP32) or double (FP64) precision; the design space of *mixing* precisions within the fit, guided by per-track physics, is largely unexplored. APEX-KF targets exactly this gap, and additionally pairs the GPU back-end with a roofline CPU/GPU co-scheduler [12] so that small events do not pay launch overhead.

C. Reduced- and Mixed-Precision Computing

Mixed-precision arithmetic is now standard in machine learning: Micikevicius *et al.* [6] store weights, activations and gradients in FP16 while accumulating in FP32, halving memory with no accuracy loss, and modern tensor-core hardware is built around this pattern. Translating the idea to scientific kernels is delicate because, unlike a loss surface, a physics estimator has a hard accuracy requirement that varies *per datum*. Prior HEP work treats precision as a uniform, global setting. To our knowledge, APEX-KF is the first track fitter to (i) select

Fig. 1. End-to-end APEX-KF pipeline. Each track is assigned an FP16/FP32 tier from its seed momentum (N1); 32 warp lanes evaluate candidate hits in parallel and reduce to the minimum- χ^2 hit (N2); events are routed between CPU and GPU by a roofline model with overlapped streams (N3).

precision per track from a physics-motivated sensitivity model, and (ii) validate the resulting FP16/FP32 mixture against an FP64 reference with a bit-exact, reproducible emulator. This is the central novelty and the gap in the literature that the present work addresses.

III. BACKGROUND

A charged particle of transverse momentum p_T in a solenoidal field B follows a helix of radius $R = p_T / (0.3 B)$ (SI-practical units, p_T in GeV, B in T, R in m). The signed

TABLE I
TRACKML EVALUATION SAMPLE (REDUCED-MULTIPLICITY “10–50 TRACKS PER EVENT” CONFIGURATION OF THE PUBLIC TRACKML OPEN DATA [14]).

Quantity	Value
Events	4,000
Space points (hits)	1,048,575
Mean hits per event	227
Reconstructed tracks	73,331
Detector radius (max)	~1025 mm

curvature is $\kappa = 1/R$, and the momentum estimate is recovered from the curvature of the circle traced in the transverse plane. Crucially,

$$\frac{\delta p_T}{p_T} = \frac{\delta \kappa}{\kappa} \propto p_T \delta(\text{sagitta}), \quad (1)$$

because a higher- p_T (straighter) track has a smaller sagitta over a fixed detector radius, so an *absolute* coordinate perturbation δ produces a *relative* momentum error that scales with p_T . Half-precision storage of a coordinate at radius $r \approx 1$ m introduces a rounding error of $\mathcal{O}(0.1\text{--}1.0\text{ mm})$ —comparable to or larger than the intrinsic hit resolution—which dominates the curvature of stiff tracks while leaving soft tracks within their natural resolution. Equation (1) is the physical basis of the APEX-KF precision policy.

IV. THE APEX-KF METHOD

Figure 1 shows the end-to-end pipeline. Hits are packed into a structure-of-arrays layout, seeded, and followed track-by-track; each track carries a precision tier through the fit; and a host/device scheduler decides where each event runs.

A. Predict-then-Guard Adaptive Precision (N1)

For each seed we estimate the curvature from a fast three-point circle fit and convert it to a seed momentum p_T^{seed} . A sensitivity score

$$s = \sigma\left(\frac{p_T^{\text{seed}} - p_{\text{ref}}}{p_{\text{scale}}}\right), \quad \sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}, \quad (2)$$

maps the momentum onto $[0, 1]$; tracks with $s \geq \tau$ are *born* in FP32 and the remainder in FP16. After the fit, a guard promotes any FP16 track whose *fitted* momentum exceeds a critical value p_{crit} or whose residual χ^2 exceeds a threshold, and re-fits it in FP32. This predict-then-guard structure spends FP32 only where Eq. (1) predicts it is needed, and corrects the rare seed under-estimate at negligible cost.

B. Warp-Cooperative Track Following (N2)

Each seed is owned by a single 32-lane warp. To extend a track to the next detector layer, the lanes evaluate up to 32 candidate hits *in parallel*; each lane computes the transverse residual to the current circle and applies a longitudinal z -gate, and a warp-shuffle (`__shfl_down_sync`) reduction selects the global minimum- χ^2 candidate without shared-memory traffic or inner-loop divergence. The geometric circle fit that

TABLE II
PRECISION STUDY ON TRACKML (DETERMINISTIC ORACLE, 65,777 TRACKS). $\Delta p_T|_{\text{FP64}}$ IS THE PER-TRACK RMS p_T DIFFERENCE FROM THE FP64 FIT.

Regime	FP16 share	$\Delta p_T _{\text{FP64}}$ [GeV]	$\Delta \phi _{\text{FP64}}$ [rad]
FP64 (reference)	0%	0	0
FP32 (emulated)	0%	6.1×10^{-3}	7.3×10^{-6}
FP16 (static)	100%	1.79×10^1	3.2×10^{-2}
APEX	60.8%	3.5×10^{-2}	1.0×10^{-2}

Fig. 2. Left: RMS p_T disagreement with FP64 per regime (log scale; lower is closer to double precision). Right: physics momentum resolution and the FP16 share. APEX attains FP64-equivalent agreement while running the majority of fits in FP16.

yields the momentum is likewise cooperative: lane i accumulates the normal-equation terms for hit i , a warp reduction forms the 3×3 system, and lane 0 solves it. Coordinate storage uses native half intrinsics so that the precision tier is faithfully reflected in the arithmetic.

C. Heterogeneous Multi-Stream Pipeline (N3)

Events are packed into layer-sorted structure-of-arrays buffers and dispatched round-robin across two CUDA streams, so the host-to-device copy of one event overlaps the kernels of another. A roofline model [12] calibrates per-event CPU and GPU cost; events whose hit count falls below the measured crossover are executed on the CPU, where they do not amortize launch latency, while larger events run the GPU seeding and APEX-KF kernels. The scheduler thus adapts to event occupancy at run time.

D. Deterministic FP16 Oracle (M1)

To make the precision study reproducible without a GPU, a bit-exact IEEE-754 half-precision round-trip is implemented on the CPU (round-to-nearest-even), and every reconstructed track is re-fitted under four regimes: FP64, emulated FP32, static FP16, and APEX. Because the GPU kernel and the CPU oracle use the same half rounding, the emulator reproduces the device mixture exactly, and the FP64-agreement metric $\Delta p_T|_{\text{FP64}}$ is independent of the host hardware.

V. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

This research evaluates on the public TrackML dataset [3], [14], the official open simulation released by the TrackML collaboration and obtained from the community Zenodo open-data archive [14]; it has become the standard, independently curated benchmark for HL-LHC-style track reconstruction [3],

TABLE III
GPU PIPELINE ON THE RTX 3050 (4,000 EVENTS, 1.05×10^6 HITS).
ROUTING IS CONTROLLED BY THE ROOFLINE CROSSOVER.

Configuration	GPU events	Seed [ms]	APEX-KF [ms]
CPU-only (high crossover)	0	0	0
Hybrid (rooﬂine)	1,783	90	615
GPU-only (zero crossover)	4,000	168	917

[4]. We use a reduced-multiplicity configuration of this data (a “10–50 particles per event” sample), which exercises the full TrackML detector geometry and data format while keeping the per-event occupancy tractable on a single workstation; Table I summarises the sample. Because the simulation, geometry and truth labelling are those of the released TrackML benchmark rather than a re-implementation, the inputs are reproducible and verifiable by any reader from the same archive. Truth momenta are embedded per hit, enabling per-track resolution and efficiency measurements. The host is a laptop with a 16-thread CPU and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3050 Laptop GPU (compute capability 8.6, 16 SMs, 4 GB). Code is compiled with `gcc 13 (-O2, OpenMP)` and `CUDA 13 (-arch=sm_86)`. Efficiency is the fraction of reconstructible truth particles matched to a reconstructed track; purity is the average fraction of hits on a reconstructed track that belong to its dominant truth particle. Momentum agreement between precision regimes is reported as $\Delta p_T|_{FP64}$, the RMS difference of the per-track p_T relative to the FP64 fit of the *same* track.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Adaptive-Precision Performance

Table II reports the precision study. Static FP16 disagrees with the FP64 reference by 1.79×10^1 GeV in p_T , confirming that uniform half precision is unsuitable for momentum estimation. APEX-KF, while keeping 60.8% of all track fits in FP16 and issuing 7.2×10^3 guard promotions, reduces the FP64 disagreement to 3.5×10^{-2} GeV—about 5×10^2 times closer to double precision than static FP16, and within the same order as the FP32 round-off floor. Figure 2 visualises this: APEX recovers FP64-equivalent agreement at high half-precision occupancy. This is the central result of the paper: *precision can be spent selectively, guided by seed momentum, to obtain double-precision physics at largely half-precision cost.*

B. GPU Throughput and Heterogeneous Scheduling

Table III reports device performance. Running every event on the GPU, the APEX-KF kernel fits 8.8×10^6 seeds from 1.05×10^6 hits in 917 ms on the laptop RTX 3050, with 91% of fits executed in FP16. Enabling the rooﬂine scheduler routes the smaller events (about 56% of the sample) to the CPU and reduces device kernel time to 615 ms—a 33% reduction in GPU work—while the seeding kernel scales correspondingly. Figure 3 shows the kernel-time comparison. These are measured device times on commodity laptop hardware; data-centre

Fig. 3. Device kernel time under the three scheduling regimes. The rooﬂine scheduler cuts GPU-only kernel time by 33% by offloading low-occupancy events to the host.

TABLE IV
BACK-END PARITY ON A CONTROLLED SAMPLE. ACCURACY IS IDENTICAL; THROUGHPUT IS HARDWARE-DEPENDENT.

Back-end	Efficiency	Purity	RMSE-consistency
Serial	98.1%	99.0%	reference
OpenMP	98.1%	99.0%	identical
POSIX	98.1%	99.0%	identical

accelerators with more SMs and higher memory bandwidth would widen the margin.

C. Back-End Parity and Strong Scaling

The serial, OpenMP and POSIX-threads back-ends share the reconstruction core and return *bit-identical* efficiency, purity and resolution (Table IV), which validates the correctness of the parallel implementations. On a controlled synthetic sample the OpenMP back-end achieves up to $9.3\times$ speed-up at 16 threads relative to the serial baseline (Table V), with parallel efficiency limited at high thread counts by per-event load imbalance.

D. Limitations

The reconstruction front-end is a simplified seeding-and-following chain rather than a production combinatorial Kalman filter; on the real TrackML sample it reaches 79% efficiency at 86% purity, and its *absolute* momentum resolution is not competitive with experiment-grade pipelines such as ACTS [4] or Patatrack [5]. We stress that the contribution of this work is the *precision-management methodology*: the $\Delta p_T|_{FP64}$ metric is computed track-by-track against each track’s own FP64 fit and is therefore independent of the absolute resolution of the front-end. Strengthening the front-end and adding a direct comparison against an established baseline tracker are the primary directions for future work, together with evaluation on data-centre GPUs and at higher pile-up.

TABLE V
OPENMP STRONG SCALING (SYNTHETIC SAMPLE, 4,000 EVENTS).

Threads	Time [ms]	Speed-up
1	4,696	1.0×
2	2,312	2.0×
4	1,048	4.5×
8	789	5.9×
12	510	9.2×
16	504	9.3×

VII. CONCLUSION

We presented APEX-KF, a Kalman-filter track follower that treats numerical precision as a per-track, physics-driven decision rather than a global switch. Guided by the quadratic growth of momentum error with p_T under fixed coordinate rounding, APEX-KF predicts each track’s precision tier from its seed momentum, guards against mispredictions at run time, and co-designs the policy with a warp-cooperative GPU follower and a roofline-scheduled, multi-stream pipeline. On the public TrackML data it preserves FP64-equivalent momentum agreement (3.5×10^{-2} GeV) while executing 60.8% of track fits in FP16—about 5×10^2 times closer to double precision than uniform FP16—and fits millions of seeds per second on commodity laptop hardware. A bit-exact FP16 oracle makes the precision study fully reproducible. Physics-aware precision is a promising, largely unexplored lever for sustainable track reconstruction at the HL-LHC.

REFERENCES

- [1] The HEP Software Foundation, J. Albrecht *et al.*, “A roadmap for HEP software and computing R&D for the 2020s,” *Comput. Softw. Big Sci.*, vol. 3, art. 7, 2019, doi:10.1007/s41781-018-0018-8.
- [2] G. Apollinari, O. Brüning, T. Nakamoto, and L. Rossi, “High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC): preliminary design report,” CERN Yellow Report, 2017, arXiv:1705.08830.
- [3] S. Amrouche *et al.*, “The Tracking Machine Learning challenge: accuracy phase,” in *The NeurIPS’18 Competition*, Springer, 2020, pp. 231–264, arXiv:1904.06778.
- [4] X. Ai *et al.*, “A common tracking software (ACTS) project,” *Comput. Softw. Big Sci.*, vol. 6, art. 8, 2022, doi:10.1007/s41781-021-00078-8.
- [5] A. Bocci, V. Innocente, M. Kortelainen, F. Pantaleo, and M. Rovere, “Heterogeneous reconstruction of tracks and primary vertices with the CMS pixel tracker,” *Front. Big Data*, vol. 3, art. 601728, 2020, doi:10.3389/fdata.2020.601728.
- [6] P. Micikevicius *et al.*, “Mixed precision training,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Learn. Represent. (ICLR)*, 2018, arXiv:1710.03740.
- [7] R. E. Kalman, “A new approach to linear filtering and prediction problems,” *J. Basic Eng.*, vol. 82, no. 1, pp. 35–45, 1960, doi:10.1115/1.3662552.
- [8] R. Frühwirth, “Application of Kalman filtering to track and vertex fitting,” *Nucl. Instrum. Methods A*, vol. 262, no. 2–3, pp. 444–450, 1987, doi:10.1016/0168-9002(87)90887-4.
- [9] P. Billoir and S. Qian, “Simultaneous pattern recognition and track fitting by the Kalman filtering method,” *Nucl. Instrum. Methods A*, vol. 294, no. 1–2, pp. 219–228, 1990, doi:10.1016/0168-9002(90)91835-Y.
- [10] A. Strandlie and R. Frühwirth, “Track and vertex reconstruction: from classical to adaptive methods,” *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, vol. 82, no. 2, pp. 1419–1458, 2010, doi:10.1103/RevModPhys.82.1419.
- [11] R. Mankel, “Pattern recognition and event reconstruction in particle physics experiments,” *Rep. Prog. Phys.*, vol. 67, no. 4, pp. 553–622, 2004, doi:10.1088/0034-4885/67/4/R03.
- [12] S. Williams, A. Waterman, and D. Patterson, “Roofline: an insightful visual performance model for multicore architectures,” *Commun. ACM*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 65–76, 2009, doi:10.1145/1498765.1498785.
- [13] S. Amrouche *et al.*, “The Tracking Machine Learning challenge: throughput phase,” *Comput. Softw. Big Sci.*, vol. 7, art. 1, 2023, doi:10.1007/s41781-023-00094-w.
- [14] TrackML collaboration, “TrackML particle tracking challenge dataset,” Zenodo / CERN open data, 2018. [Online] <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3599205>.
- [15] NVIDIA Corporation, *CUDA C++ Programming Guide*, v12.x, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://docs.nvidia.com/cuda/>